

Revisiting the Literature of Behavioural Finance in the Stock Market: A Bibliometric Analysis and Potential Future Research Directions

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Abstract

Background: Over the past two decades, research on behavioural finance in stock markets has grown rapidly, reflecting the increasing academic and practical relevance of psychological and cognitive factors in financial decision-making. However, existing reviews remain fragmented, either limited to specific databases or focusing on partial aspects, such as institutional investors or market anomalies. This situation highlights the need for a more comprehensive mapping of behavioural finance research in stock markets.

Objectives: This study uses the Scopus database to review research trends in behavioural finance in stock markets. Specifically, it aims to identify key themes, analyse intellectual structures, and explore potential directions for future research.

Methodology: This study employed a combination of bibliometric analysis and content analysis, following the PRISMA protocol. Data were collected from the Scopus databases based on inclusion-exclusion criteria. A total of 108 articles were published from 2002 to 2025, including

reviews. The data were analysed using various software programmes, including the R-Biblioshiny, VOSviewer, and Harzing-PoP.

Results: Findings indicate a significant increase in publications on behavioural finance in stock markets, with leading journals such as the *Journal of Behavioural Finance* (JBF), *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets* (QRFM), *Journal of Economic Behaviour & Organisation* (JEBO), and *Quantitative Finance* (QF). Asia and Europe dominate research output. Four thematic clusters have been identified: (1) individual investor decisions, (2) investor behaviour in market efficiency, (3) investor sentiment, and (4) investor behaviour in emerging stock markets.

Conclusion: This study concludes that behavioural finance explains market inefficiency and anomalies. Research in this field continues to grow globally, with increasing attention paid to sentiment, heuristics, and investor behaviour in emerging markets.

Unique Contribution: The study offers an integrated overview of intellectual trends and thematic clusters, laying the groundwork for the development of theory and practice in this field.

Key Recommendation: Future studies are recommended to expand data sources beyond Scopus, normalise citation metrics, and conduct cross-country comparisons, particularly in underrepresented regions. In addition, regulators and policymakers are encouraged to integrate behavioural insights into financial literacy programmes and market regulatory frameworks to improve efficiency and investor protection.

Keywords: Stock market, behavioural finance, investor behaviour, bibliometric analysis

Introduction

Over the past two decades, behavioural finance has grown rapidly, emphasising that investor decisions are influenced by economic information and psychological, cognitive, and emotional factors. Evidence suggests that even in pessimistic market conditions, investment growth can persist despite weakening investor sentiment, highlighting the significant role of investor psychology in shaping market dynamics. These findings challenge classical theories such as the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) by demonstrating systematic deviations due to behavioural and social factors (Sharma & Kumar, 2020; Woo et al., 2020).

Various studies have shown that behavioural biases, such as overconfidence, anchoring, representativeness, and herding, contribute to market volatility and investment anomalies. These biases lead to systematic deviations from rationality, ultimately impacting stock prices and market efficiency. Therefore, behavioural finance has emerged as an alternative framework to classical theory, including EMH, in explaining complex market phenomena (Gupta & Shrivastava, 2023). One of the most extensively studied aspects is investor sentiment, which has been proven to play a significant role in stock price uncertainty and exhibits predictive power over market dynamics (Akin & Akin, 2024).

Global research confirms that psychological and cognitive aspects play an essential role in investment decision-making, as demonstrated by the GameStop short squeeze phenomenon, the development of sentiment indices, and the increasing participation of retail investors (Akin & Akin, 2024; Póra, 2022). The democratisation of trading through digital platforms and the role of social media further underscore the importance of sentiment analysis in anticipating market instability (Póra, 2022). Although the Efficient Market Hypothesis has been extensively tested,

various behavioural anomalies doubt its validity (Woo et al., 2020). Therefore, integrating behavioural factors into modern financial frameworks is essential for understanding the complexity of market dynamics.

Furthermore, Cross-country studies reveal diverse research focuses. In India, behavioural biases influence investment decisions through excessive reactions to corporate earnings. Research in the US and China highlights investor sentiment, while interest in trading behaviour has declined. The COVID-19 pandemic has reinforced the dominance of overconfidence and disposition effects in investment decisions. Similar phenomena were observed in Brazil with market crashes and uneven recovery. In Spain, through the role of trust and fear in the crisis cycle, and in Malaysia, with NLP-FinBERT findings linking retail investor emotions to market trends (Yeoh et al., 2025)

Although behavioural finance literature has grown rapidly, most previous reviews remain systematic or conceptual in nature (Póra, 2022; Sharma & Kumar, 2020; Woo et al., 2020), with some limited to specific aspects such as institutional investor behaviour. Bibliometric analysis and systematic review related to the topic have been conducted by Gokhale and Mittal (2024) using the Web of Science (WoS) database only. Furthermore, the literature review by Gupta and Shrivastava (2023) examines only critical reviews related to behavioural finance, using Pareto analysis, and focuses on behavioural biases and investor decisions within the context of heuristic theory. Additionally, a bibliometric review related to the topic has been conducted by Kumar and Choudhary (2023). However, it is limited to scholarly filtration, language filtration, and subject filtration, without content analysis. Hence, to fill this research gap and complement the bibliometric findings by Gokhale and Mittal (2024), this study is considered crucial for providing a significant contribution to the literature.

To date, no Scopus-based bibliometric study has comprehensively mapped the trends, knowledge structure, and central themes of behavioural finance in stock markets, combining with content analysis. This study addresses this gap by: (1) tracking the evolution of publications, geographical distribution, institutional collaboration, and intellectual influence; (2) identifying thematic clusters and knowledge structures; and (3) exploring research gaps to enhance theoretical and practical understanding. Accordingly, this study formulates three research questions (RQs):

- RQ1.* How has behavioural finance research in stock markets evolved, as seen from publication trends, geographical distribution, institutional collaboration, and intellectual influence?
- RQ2.* What thematic clusters and knowledge structures can be identified in the behavioural finance and stock market literature?
- RQ3.* What critical research gaps remain, and how can future studies enhance theoretical and practical understanding of behavioural finance in stock markets?

Methods

Research design

This study employs a quantitative approach, utilising bibliometric analysis from the Scopus database and content analysis to gain deeper insights. A similar approach was adopted by Alimusa et al. (2024) to synthesise the research flow in Scopus-indexed journals from 2002 to 2025.

Search strategy, criteria and data collection

For the data search, this study followed the PRISMA guidelines outlined by Zakaria et al. (2021). Figure 1 illustrates the flow diagram of the PRISMA protocol applied in this research. Data was collected on April 7, 2025, from the Scopus database using the keywords ("Behavioural Finance" and "Investor Behaviour" OR "Market Sentiment" and "Stock Market" or "Equity Market" or "Share Market" or "Capital Market"). An initial search of the Scopus database yielded 143 records. Titles, abstracts, and keywords were screened to ensure relevance to the themes of behavioural finance and stock markets. To maintain quality and consistency, three inclusion criteria were applied: articles written in English only, journal document sources only, and articles published only. The exclusion criteria included non-article document types (such as conference papers, book chapters, reviews, and books), non-journal source types, and articles published in languages other than English. After applying these criteria, 35 records were removed, leaving 108 articles that met the criteria. These selected articles were then used for descriptive analysis, bibliometric mapping, and content analysis.

Tools and data analysis

To achieve its objectives, this study utilised several analytical tools. R-Biblioshiny and VOSviewer were used to map bibliometric networks, visualise keyword patterns, and analyse research streams. The Publish or Perish (PoP) software by Harzing calculates citation indicators and identifies the most influential documents. By combining bibliometric techniques with content analysis, this study provides a structured approach to investigating behavioural finance in stock market research. This framework identifies key trends such as publication growth, leading countries and institutions, core journals, influential academics, keyword co-occurrence, and emerging research themes.

Figure 1. Data processing and search strategy

Results

Descriptive analysis

In this section, the authors examined publications from 2002 to 2025, with a primary focus on journal articles. The earliest research, conducted by Daniel et al. (2002), explored investor psychology within capital markets, particularly in the context of behavioural finance in the stock market. An analysis of the development of scientific publications in this field indicates an annual growth rate of 6.21%. These publications receive an average of 85 citations per year, with 18.10 citations per paper and 6,297 references (see Table 1).

Table 1. Descriptive information

Description (metrics)	Result (data)
Publication years (period)	2002 – 2025
Total documents	108
Number of citations	1955
Citation Years	23 (2002 – 2025)
Citations per Year	85
Average citation per Paper	18.10
h_index	24
g_index	41
Author keyword	389
Author	257
Sources	79

Authors of single-authored docs	10
International co-authorship	16.18%
References	6297
Co-author pe doc	2.58
Annual growth rate	6.21%

Figure 2 presents an annual publication trend from 2002 to 2025. The number of publications began to increase significantly in 2022, reaching 14 total publications. This shows that the focus on the behaviour of finance in the stock market has become an increasingly important issue among researchers.

Figure 2. Number of publications per year

Research trend analysis

Figure 3 illustrates that the relevant field of study for this topic encompasses publications in Economics, Economics and Finance, Business, Management, and Accounting, as well as Social Sciences. The subject areas of Economics and Finance occupy the top position with 43.8%, followed by Management and Accounting with 27.8%, Social Sciences with 9.1%, and Psychology with 4.0%.

Figure 3. Subject area

Meanwhile, Table 2 shows that of the 10 most popular journals related to the issue of behavioral finance in stock market based on the number of publications (TP), it was found that the *Journal of Banking and Finance* is the most popular journal with 6 TP (5.56%), followed by *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets* with 5 TP (4.63%), then the *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization*, and *Quantitative Finance*, each with 4 TP (7.2%). It shows that the publication of behavioral finance in the stock market is most often published in the top Scopus Q1 journals such as the *Journal of Banking and Finance (JBF)*, *Qualitative Research in Financial Markets (QRFM)*, *Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization (JEBO)*, and *Quantitative Finance (QF)*. Furthermore, to complete and sharpen our analysis, we analysed total citations (TC), average citations per publication (C/P), h-index and g-index using R Studio (R-Biblioshiny). Therefore, based on the results of the analysis of journal local impact using R-biblioshiny, the *QF* is the leading journal based on TC (177 TC). Thus, most publications related to behavioural finance in the stock market originate from top-tier Scopus journals and reputable publishers.

Table 2. The ten most popular journals

No.	Source Title and Scopus rank	Publisher	TP	%	TC	C/P	h	g
1	<i>Journal of Banking and Finance (Q1)</i>	Elsevier B.V.	6	5,56	144	24.0	5	6
2	<i>Qualitative Research in Financial Markets (Q2)</i>	Emerald Publishing	5	4.63	106	21.2	5	5
3	<i>Journal of Economic Behavior and Organization (Q1)</i>	Elsevier B.V.	4	7.20	172	43.0	4	4
4	<i>Quantitative Finance (Q1)</i>	Taylor and Francis Ltd.	4	7.20	177	44.3	4	4
5	<i>International Journal of Financial Studies (Q2)</i>	MDPI	3	4.17	5	1.67	1	2
6	<i>Investment Management and Financial Innovations (Q3)</i>	Business Perspectives	3	4.17	6	2.00	1	2
7	<i>Journal of Behavioral Finance (Q2)</i>	Taylor and Francis Ltd.	3	4.17	16	5.33	3	3
8	<i>Review of Behavioral Finance (Q2)</i>	Emerald Publishing	3	4.17	150	50.0	2	3
9	<i>Afro-Asian Journal of Finance and Accounting (Q4)</i>	Inderscience Enterprises Ltd	2	2.78	2	1.00	1	1
10	<i>Benchmarking (Q1)</i>	Emerald Publishing	2	2.78	9	4.50	1	2

Note(s): TP=total number of publications;TC=total citations; C/P=average citations per publication; and h=h-index; g=g-index.

Most influential countries, affiliates, and productive authors

Table 3 presents the analysis of ten leading countries from 39 countries related to the topic, with India occupying the top position with 23 TP (21.3%), followed by China with 14 TP (12.96%),

the United States with 12 TP (11.11%), and Malaysia with 9 TP (8.33%). Most of the countries on this list are from Asia and Europe, indicating a concentration of intense research interest in these regions. Meanwhile, contributions from the American region are relatively limited. This gap highlights the importance of strengthening cross-regional research collaboration on behavioural finance in the stock market, particularly in increasing the role of countries from regions whose contributions are currently underrepresented. Table 4 describes the top ten institutions based on their scientific contributions in this field. At the peak of this list is Universiti Sains Malaysia, with 5 TP (4.63%), which underscores its leading position in stock market research.

Table 3. The top 10 Countries contributed to the literature

Country	TP	(%)	TC	C/P	Continent
India	23	21.30	271	11.8	Asia
China	14	12.96	249	17.8	Asia
United State	12	11.11	95	7.92	North America
Malaysia	9	8.33	180	20.0	Asia
United Kingdom	7	6.48	67	9.57	Europe
Pakistan	6	5.56	37	6.17	Asia
Spain	5	4.63	141	28.2	Europe
Brazil	4	3.70	12	3.00	South America
Taiwan	4	3.70	117	29.3	Asia
Netherlands	3	2.78	61	20.3	Europe

Table 4. The top 10 institutions contributed to the publications

Institution	TP	%	Country
Universiti Sains Malaysia	5	4.63	Malaysia
Universiti Publica de Navarra	4	3.70	Spanyol
Punjabi University	3	2.78	India
Thammasat Universiti	3	2.78	Thailand
Universiti Teknologi MARA	2	1.85	Malaysia
National Changhua University of Education	2	1.85	Taiwan
HebrewUniversity of Jerusalem	2	1.85	Israel
Nanjing University of Finance and Economics	2	1.85	Tionggok
Dongbei University of Finance and Economics	2	1.85	Tionggok
Universidad de Zaragosa	2	1.85	Spanyol

Table 5. Top ten most cited documents

Title	TC	C/Y	Source and Scopus rank
Investor psychology in capital markets: Evidence and policy implications	380	16.52	<i>Journal of Monetary Economics (Q1)</i>
Does herding affect volatility? Implications	116	8.92	<i>Quantitative Finance</i>

for the Spanish stock market				(Q1)
Evaluation of behavioral biases affecting investment decision making of individual equity investors by fuzzy analytic hierarchy process	104	20.80		<i>Review of Behavioral Finance (Q2)</i>
Investor mood and financial markets	79	5.27		<i>Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization (Q1)</i>
Market sentiment: A key factor of investors' imitative behaviour	63	4.85		<i>Accounting and Finance</i>
Behavioural finance perspectives on Malaysian stock market efficiency	53	5.89		<i>Borsa Istanbul Review</i>
Technical analysis and individual investors	52	4.73		<i>Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization (Q1)</i>
Social simulation of stock markets: Taking it to the next level	51	2.83		<i>JASSS (Q1)</i>
Sentiment and stock returns: The SAD anomaly revisited	50	3.33		<i>Journal of Banking and Finance (Q1)</i>
Behavioral mediators of financial decision making – a state-of-art literature review	380	16.52		<i>Journal of Monetary Economics (Q1)</i>

The study results show that research on investor psychology and financial market behaviour has significantly developed in the last two decades. The highest cited literature consistently highlights the importance of psychological approaches in understanding individual and institutional financial decisions. Table 5 presents the seminal article by Daniel et al. (2002), which features 380 TC, as evidence of the strong influence of the behavioural economics approach in explaining capital market dynamics. Other researchers, such as Blasco et al. (2012) and Jain et al. (2020), enrich this realm by exploring factors such as market sentiment and behavioural biases, employing complex methodological approaches, including fuzzy-AHP. These findings strengthen the argument that the study of investor behaviour has shifted from a classical economic framework to a more complex and adaptive multidisciplinary approach in response to modern market conditions.

Keyword analysis

Keyword analysis can be strengthened by additional insights into research trends obtained through the VOSviewer visualisation, which identified 17 keywords that met the threshold of a minimum co-occurrence of 3 out of 389 analysed. These keywords are categorised into four distinct groups, as illustrated in Figure 4. This figure presents a thematic map of the conceptual structure of keywords in the literature on behavioural finance in stock markets, providing a more detailed understanding of the main themes explored in this field. Additional information regarding the research stream can be found in Table 7

Figure 4. VOSviewer visualisation of keyword co-occurrence

Note(s): Unit of analysis = All keywords; Counting method: Full counting; keyword co-occurrence = 3; meet the threshold = 17

Furthermore, the analysis of the thematic map using R-Biblioshiny in Figure 5, based on density and centrality, reveals four quadrants. These results were obtained using a semi-automatic algorithm that reviewed the titles of all references related to the research object.

Figure 5. Thematic map based on the author’s keyword
Source: Author's elaboration from R-Biblioshiny

Thus, Figure 4 and Table 6 present four research groups based on keyword co-occurrences. The cartographic analysis, which employs the co-occurrence method, enables us to create groups and identify the primary themes of the most frequently published behavioural finance in stock market papers. Following the study by Alimusa et al. (2024), we find that the first group deals with individual investor decisions. The second group identifies the relationship between investor behaviour and market efficiency. In the third group, we group investor sentiment in general. The last group deals with investor behaviour in the emerging stock markets.

Table 6. Cluster of research streams

Keywords	Item	Co-occurrence	Total link strength	Cluster/theme
Cluster 1 (red)	5			Individual investor decision
decision making		6	8	
Individual investor		4	8	
Investment		6	14	
Investments		7	28	
Trading		3	6	
Cluster 2 (green)	5			Investor behaviour in market efficiency
Asset pricing		5	6	
behavioural finance		70	92	
Capital markets		3	6	
Investor psychology		3	9	
Market efficiency		4	11	
Cluster 3 (blue)	5			Investor sentiment behaviour
Commerce		6	24	
Herding		4	12	
Investor sentiment		17	39	
Overconfidence		7	16	
Stock market		23	53	
Cluster 4 (orange)	2			Investor behaviour in the emerging stock market
Emerging stock markets		4	4	
Investor behaviour		21	32	

Source: author elaboration from VOSviewer

Discussion

Content analysis

To address RQ2, we conducted a content analysis to investigate the literature research stream on behavioural finance in the stock market.

Cluster 1. Individual investor decision

Behavioural finance theory emphasises that investor decisions are not entirely determined by rational calculations, but are also influenced by psychological, emotional, and social factors. Empirical studies indicate that biases such as heuristics, overconfidence, and herding significantly influence stock market behaviour, although findings are often inconsistent (Sharma & Kumar, 2020). For example, research has found that men tend to engage in overtrading with poor results compared to women. However, cross-country evidence suggests that women's stability advantage does not always emerge, especially in markets with low financial literacy. Herding behaviour has also been documented in India, Pakistan, and Saudi Arabia. However, its strength is influenced by regulation, institutional quality, and cultural norms (Shefrin, 2024). Methodologically, most research still relies on surveys or cross-sectional data, making it challenging to test causal relationships, while studies using real trading data or longitudinal designs remain limited. An important unanswered question is how behavioural biases interact with digital innovations such as robo-advisors and algorithmic trading, and whether technology can balance biases or reinforce irrationality by creating new echo chambers for retail investors. Therefore, future research should adopt cross-cultural and longitudinal approaches with a focus on gender differences, financial literacy, and the influence of technology on modern investment behaviour.

Cluster 2. Investor behaviour in market efficiency

Behavioural finance literature emphasises that investor behaviour is important in influencing market efficiency. Evidence suggests that psychological biases, such as overconfidence, anchoring, and representativeness, trigger market anomalies and undermine the assumptions of the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH). At the same time, institutional behaviour such as speculation can also disrupt market stability. Although the EMH provides a basic framework, market efficiency is dynamic, as explained in the Adaptive Market Hypothesis (AMH), which emphasises the influence of market conditions and investor behaviour (Saldanha et al., 2025). Additionally, investors' preferences for environmental, social, and governance (ESG) factors reveal behavioural dynamics not fully explained by classical theory. Bibliometric studies also confirm the growing academic attention to the relationship between behaviour and market efficiency by Gokhale and Mittal (2024). However, most evidence still comes from emerging markets, and many studies rely on historical data, which limits the ability to conduct causal testing. Therefore, adaptive models incorporating bounded rationality, sentiment dynamics, information asymmetry, and policies responsive to investor psychology are urgently needed to minimise deviations from market efficiency.

Cluster 3. Investor sentiment behaviour

Investor sentiment has been extensively studied as an essential factor in market dynamics. Studies show excessive focus on specific assets, such as cryptocurrencies, can trigger mispricing and price anomalies. Sentiment also influences the profitability of value and momentum strategies, particularly in markets with information constraints. The most apparent manifestation is herding, which is triggered by emotions and information constraints and has been shown to increase short-term volatility, especially in emerging markets. Efforts to measure sentiment

through composite indices and high-frequency data have predictive value (Li et al., 2023), but consistency across methods remains a challenge, necessitating standardization of measurement to enhance cross-country comparability, in addition to technical factors, psychological and demographic dimensions such as gender differences, personality, and financial literacy moderating the relationship between sentiment and investment behavior (Gupta & Shrivastava, 2023). However, most studies are cross-sectional, thus failing to explain how sentiment patterns evolve during crises such as pandemics or geopolitical shocks. Therefore, future research should combine longitudinal designs and cross-cultural perspectives while testing the effectiveness of interventions such as emotion-based financial literacy or adaptive regulation to control herding (Gokhale & Mittal, 2024).

Cluster 4. Investor behaviour in the emerging stock market

Literature shows that psychological and non-economic factors influence investor behaviour in emerging stock markets. Cross-regional studies confirm that investor sentiment and market attention play a significant role in determining asset prices, both in the short and long term. Evidence from the Dhaka Stock Exchange and African exchanges suggests that sentiment, weather, and other external factors often outweigh economic fundamentals. This demonstrates that the behavioural finance framework can explain market dynamics in developing countries with weak regulation, contrary to the assumption of efficient markets (Akin & Akin, 2024). However, most of this research focuses on short-term relationships, leaving long-term mechanisms and policy implications understudied.

These findings confirm that investor behaviour in emerging markets cannot be separated from the social context and systemic crises. However, research often fails to integrate institutional and cultural factors as explanatory variables. Other factors, such as stock price affordability, profit expectations, and media coverage, influence investment decisions (Daniel et al., 2002). However, a research gap exists in linking macro variables (e.g., interest rates, inflation, or geopolitical turmoil) with behavioural biases in emerging markets. Therefore, future research should adopt a multidisciplinary approach that combines psychology, economics, and big data to understand how investor behaviour in emerging markets contributes to global volatility and the transmission of financial crises.

Future research directions

Bibliometric findings reveal several gaps that can form the basis for future research directions. We also propose several potential future research areas and offer recommendations based on the literature from the past three years. Thus, to answer *RQ3*, these findings provide potential future research directions, as presented in Table 7, which have not been studied further.

Table 7. Potential future research directions

Future research directions	References
1. Investigating the impact of cultural differences on the relationship between behavioural financial factors, risk perception, and investment decision-making	Bhutto <i>et al.</i> (2025), Authors' suggestions
2. Following up on factors that influence investment decisions	

from the perspective of institutional investors	
3. Further research on the influence of behavioural bias factors on decision-making that is differentiated based on gender, religion, culture, education level, investment objectives, and income	
4. Investigating factors determining behavioural finance-based regulations on market efficiency	Gokhale and Mittal (2024), Akintoye (2008),
5. Redeveloping the EMH theory to test the influence of cognitive or emotional biases, creating market price anomalies and inefficiencies	Authors' suggestions
6. Future research could examine whether markets across and within countries offer diversification benefits using the AMH approach	Mallikarjunappa <i>et al.</i> (2025),
7. Future research should integrate the EMH and AMH in examining investor behaviour in efficient markets	Gokhale and Mittal (2024), Saldanha <i>et al.</i> (2025).
8. Predicting investor behaviour and sentiment through factors of verconfidence, governance, demographics, political instability, and monetary policy in anticipating capital market crises	
9. Re-examining the influence of herding behaviour and overconfidence on investor behaviour sentiment through the mediating role of risk perception and dividend policy	Bhutto <i>et al.</i> (2025), Authors' suggestions
10. Development of an investor sentiment analysis model to predict volatility and investor behaviour, both individual and institutional	Póra, A. (2022), Authors' suggestions
11. Investigate behavioural bias factors in influencing investment decisions across other developing countries	

Conclusion and Research Implications

Conclusion

This study provides an important contribution to mapping the development of behavioural finance literature in stock markets through a comprehensive bibliometric approach. The findings identify at least 4 clusters on this topic, including 1) individual investor decision, 2) investor behaviour in market efficiency, 3) investor (market) sentiment, and 4) investor behaviour in emerging markets. These findings also identify several factors that influence investor behaviour, namely psychological, sociodemographic, emotional, and cognitive factors. However, there are also behavioural bias factors, such as herding behaviour, overconfidence, and irrationality, that influence investor behaviour in both developed and developing countries. Likewise, there are still weaknesses in the EMH theory in linking behavioural finance and market efficiency. Therefore, these findings contribute to the importance of integration with AMH. These findings contribute to the understanding of investor behaviour among managers and capital market players in the digital era.

Theoretical and practical implications

Theoretically, this study confirms the relevance of behavioural finance in explaining market anomalies that cannot be explained by classical theories such as the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH), while highlighting the role of the Adaptive Market Hypothesis (AMH) in assessing market efficiency under dynamic conditions. These findings enrich theoretical discussions by integrating EMH and AMH and open up opportunities for applying cognitive technology and artificial intelligence (AI) in analysing modern financial behaviour.

In practice, the findings of this study provide input for regulators, policymakers, and market participants to design behaviour-based interventions that enhance stability, financial literacy, and investor protection. FinTech solutions can be utilised to minimise biases such as overconfidence and herding. Regulators are advised to establish policies to reduce excessive biases (Daniel *et al.*, 2002), while policymakers need to strengthen investor education programmes to encourage more rational and bias-aware decision-making.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express his deepest gratitude to the Education Fund Management Institute (LPDP) under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia for its support of my doctoral studies.

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